

Harmonising narratives for future energy and raw materials demand and supply in face of climate change

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ABSTRACT

The EU's energy transition aims to mitigate climate change is reinforced by the digital transition to enhance efficiency and system integration. As this twin transition is highly materials-intensive, robust projections of raw material (RM) demand are essential to anticipate supply constraints, associated risks, and inform timely policy decisions. Given the deep uncertainties surrounding this transition, scenario storylines are needed to structure assumptions transparently and explore multiple plausible futures. Accordingly, this work develops storylines to assess future RM demand, supply and associated environmental impacts for the twin transition in 2030, 2050, and 2070, and to support industry and policy decisions enabling the transition. The narratives are co-developed through a stepwise, consensus-based process building on overarching anchor scenarios reflecting different emission pathways, and experts inputs. Further steps include identifying key driving forces and mapping their interactions and interdependencies across the key themes of interest, followed by storyline elaboration and validation by industrial stakeholders. These anchor scenarios are further extended to account for essential dimensions so far essentially ignored in state-of-the-art narratives, such as circularity or RM supply constraints. This ultimately enables to reach a more comprehensive and relevant basis for the calculation of RM demand projections as support to sound decision-making.

Keywords: Twin transition; Narratives; Critical Raw Materials, Shared Socioeconomic Pathways.

1. INTRODUCTION

A rapid global transformation of the energy sector is urgently needed to mitigate climate-change impacts [1]. Renewable and sustainable energy technologies offer the potential to generate power with negligible emissions of air pollutants [2], and are closely linked to the twin transition, aligning green and digital transformations around shared sustainability goals [3]. This transition is highly materials-intensive and depends on raw materials (RMs), including both critical and non-critical minerals and metals, required to develop and deploy these technologies [4]. Given the EU's import dependence and the deep uncertainties surrounding the twin transition, anticipating future RM demand and supply is essential. Scenario analysis can help identify emerging trends, risks, and strategic responses [5]. These analyses can be developed using narratives and scenarios. Narratives (or storylines) qualitatively describe plausible future developments and provide the logic underpinning quantitative scenarios by highlighting socio-economic, technological, and institutional conditions [6], while scenarios are internally consistent representations of how the future may unfold, based on linked qualitative and/or quantitative assumptions about major driving forces over time [6], [7]. Overall, narratives provide context and rationale, whereas scenarios combine these qualitative storylines with quantitative assumptions within a broader framework. Despite the existence of various global and EU energy scenarios [8], new uncertainties continue to emerge, contributing to an increasingly fragmented world, hindering the decarbonisation agenda, and complicating efforts to anticipate future RMs demand and supply. In this way, this work aims to develop storylines within the EU-funded RAWCLIC¹ project, which has the objective to provide projections of future RMs demand and supply, and the associated environmental impacts in 2030, 2050, and 2070 arising from the EU's twin transition, and to support evidence-based industry and policy decisions that will enable this transition.

¹Future RAW materials demand, supply and sustainability in the face of CLimate Change.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The narratives are developed through a stepwise, consensus-based process incorporating domain expert input on missing key driving factors. The first step involves i) selecting anchor scenarios from the Scenario Model Intercomparison Project (ScenarioMIP) framework under CMIP7, which provides a wide range of plausible emissions pathways for use as inputs to Earth System Models (ESMs) [9]. These anchor scenarios are based on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), which combine overarching climate goals with socio-economic drivers such as population growth and technological change [10]. As key boundary conditions, they frame the scenario space and provide a consistent basis for exploring alternative futures. The second step consists of ii) determining the driving forces, their synergies and interdependencies that will be influencing material demand, primary and secondary supply, and their associated environmental impacts. This is achieved by iii) developing cause-effect relationships using causal loop diagrams (CLDs) within the project's main domains of interest to iv) produce a master causal loop diagram, which then informs the v) elaboration of the storylines. These are then validated by the RAWCLIC consortium, the advisory board, and industrial stakeholders.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first stage of the consensus-based process selected **SSP1 VLLO**, **SSP2 Medium**, **SSP2 Low**, and **SSP2 low with geopolitical tensions** as anchor scenarios for developing the RAWCLIC storylines. SSP1 VLLO aligns with limiting warming to 1.5 °C by 2100 with limited overshoot, SSP2 Medium reflects current climate policies, and SSP2 Low is consistent with keeping warming likely below 2 °C; the geopolitics variant mainly assesses impacts on RM supply. Together, these scenarios span different climate ambitions and geopolitical risks that will shape RM demand in 2030, 2050, and 2070. Beyond anchor scenarios selection, the integrated causal-loop diagram will capture the system-wide feedbacks, translating the interdependencies and synergies among the driving forces into structured storyline elements. Particular attention will be given to dimensions often overlooked in overarching narratives, such as circularity, secondary material markets, and structural supply constraints.

4. CONCLUSION

The anchor scenarios were selected in the first stage of a stepwise, consensus-building process to develop narratives for future RMs demand and supply, and the associated environmental impacts for the twin transition in 2030, 2050, and 2070. Interactions among key driving forces will be elaborated and validated by industry and other relevant domain experts supporting the EU's twin transition. Once the scenario storylines be delegated within the project, they will be developed into narrative-based scenarios, encompassing qualitative and quantitative outputs of RAWCLIC.

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